

The flavor composition of UHE cosmic neutrinos from IceCube to an astrophysical source

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question

- ◆ Motivation: inverse problem?
- ◆ Divergent flavor distribution?
- ◆ Exact mu-tau symmetry limit
- ◆ Conclusion: accuracy matters

Is the original flavor composition as expected?

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- ◆ A neutrino telescope aims to probe the flavor distribution of high-energy astrophysical neutrinos.

- ◆ To this end, one should derive a general formula to infer the source flavors from a telescope. An early and preliminary study of this kind: L. Fu, C.M. Ho, T. Weiler 2012.

Characterization of the Three-Flavor Composition of Cosmic Neutrinos with IceCube

(IceCube Collaboration)

(Dated: October 30, 2025)

Neutrinos oscillate over cosmic distances. Using 11.4 years of IceCube data, the flavor composition of the all-sky neutrino flux from 5 TeV–10 PeV is studied. We report the first measurement down to the $\mathcal{O}(\text{TeV})$ scale using events classified into three flavor-dependent morphologies. The best fit flavor ratio is $f_e : f_\mu : f_\tau = 0.30 : 0.37 : 0.33$, consistent with the standard three-flavor neutrino oscillation model. Each fraction is constrained to be > 0 at $> 90\%$ confidence level, assuming a broken power law for cosmic neutrinos. We infer the flavor composition of cosmic neutrinos at their sources, and find production via neutron decay lies outside the 99% confidence interval.

arXiv:2510.24957v1 [astro-ph.HE] 28 Oct 2025

- ◆ Naïve idea: assume **the same flavor composition** for all the sources, to infer their **1 : 2 : 0** flavors.
- ◆ The inferred **mu** and **tau** flavor ratios are **nonsense** due to **divergence**, but **their sum** looks OK.
- ◆ This **divergence** is found to arise from an approximate **mu–tau symmetry** of lepton flavor mixing.

- ◆ The probability of neutrino oscillations in vacuum:

$$P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) = \delta_{\alpha\beta} - 4 \sum_{i < j}^3 \operatorname{Re} (U_{\alpha i} U_{\beta j} U_{\alpha j}^* U_{\beta i}^*) \sin^2 \left(1.27 \frac{\Delta m_{ji}^2}{E} L \right) + 2 \sum_{i < j}^3 \operatorname{Im} (U_{\alpha i} U_{\beta j} U_{\alpha j}^* U_{\beta i}^*) \sin \left(2.53 \frac{\Delta m_{ji}^2}{E} L \right)$$

- ◆ The oscillation length: $1.27 \frac{\Delta m_{ji}^2}{E} L_0 = \pi \longrightarrow L_0 \simeq 2.48 \frac{E}{\Delta m_{ji}^2}$ **1300 km for reactor neutrino oscillations**

- ◆ The **washout** effect: $\sin^2 \left(1.27 \frac{\Delta m_{ji}^2}{E} L \right) = \sin^2 \left(\pi \frac{L}{L_0} \right) = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cos \left(2\pi \frac{L}{L_0} \right)$

$$L \gg L_0$$

In this case neutrinos oscillate **too fast**, and a certain degree of their energy distribution makes the **cosine** term **average out** to zero.

- ◆ Energy & distance independence: $P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) = P(\bar{\nu}_\alpha \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^3 |U_{\alpha i}|^2 |U_{\beta i}|^2$

◆ **The neutrino fluxes:**

At a **neutrino telescope:**

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Phi_e \\ \Phi_\mu \\ \Phi_\tau \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P_{ee} & P_{e\mu} & P_{e\tau} \\ P_{\mu e} & P_{\mu\mu} & P_{\mu\tau} \\ P_{\tau e} & P_{\tau\mu} & P_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_e \\ \phi_\mu \\ \phi_\tau \end{bmatrix}$$

At an **astrophysical source**

$$P_{\alpha\beta} = P_{\beta\alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^3 (|U_{\alpha i}|^2 |U_{\beta i}|^2)$$

Conservation of probability:

$$\Phi_0 \equiv \Phi_e + \Phi_\mu + \Phi_\tau = \phi_e + \phi_\mu + \phi_\tau$$

◆ **The flavor fractions:**

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \eta_e \equiv \frac{\phi_e}{\Phi_0}, \quad \eta_\mu \equiv \frac{\phi_\mu}{\Phi_0}, \quad \eta_\tau \equiv \frac{\phi_\tau}{\Phi_0} \\ f_e \equiv \frac{\Phi_e}{\Phi_0}, \quad f_\mu \equiv \frac{\Phi_\mu}{\Phi_0}, \quad f_\tau \equiv \frac{\Phi_\tau}{\Phi_0} \end{array} \right. \begin{array}{l} \text{source} \\ \text{telescope} \end{array}$$

- ◆ Let us use **Gabriel Cramer's** rule to solve the equations:

$$\begin{pmatrix} P_{ee} & P_{e\mu} & P_{e\tau} \\ P_{\mu e} & P_{\mu\mu} & P_{\mu\tau} \\ P_{\tau e} & P_{\tau\mu} & P_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \eta_e \\ \eta_\mu \\ \eta_\tau \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_e \\ f_\mu \\ f_\tau \end{bmatrix}$$

$$D_0 = \begin{vmatrix} P_{ee} & P_{e\mu} & P_{e\tau} \\ P_{\mu e} & P_{\mu\mu} & P_{\mu\tau} \\ P_{\tau e} & P_{\tau\mu} & P_{\tau\tau} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$D_e = \begin{vmatrix} f_e & P_{e\mu} & P_{e\tau} \\ f_\mu & P_{\mu\mu} & P_{\mu\tau} \\ f_\tau & P_{\tau\mu} & P_{\tau\tau} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$D_\mu = \begin{vmatrix} P_{ee} & f_e & P_{e\tau} \\ P_{\mu e} & f_\mu & P_{\mu\tau} \\ P_{\tau e} & f_\tau & P_{\tau\tau} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$D_\tau = \begin{vmatrix} P_{ee} & P_{e\mu} & f_e \\ P_{\mu e} & P_{\mu\mu} & f_\mu \\ P_{\tau e} & P_{\tau\mu} & f_\tau \end{vmatrix}$$

- ◆ A trivial solution is abandoned. **Nontrivial solutions** are

$$\eta_e = \frac{D_e}{D_0}, \quad \eta_\mu = \frac{D_\mu}{D_0}, \quad \eta_\tau = \frac{D_\tau}{D_0}$$

$$D_0 = \left[|U_{e1}|^2 \left(|U_{\mu2}|^2 |U_{\tau3}|^2 - |U_{\mu3}|^2 |U_{\tau2}|^2 \right) + |U_{e2}|^2 \left(|U_{\mu3}|^2 |U_{\tau1}|^2 - |U_{\mu1}|^2 |U_{\tau3}|^2 \right) + |U_{e3}|^2 \left(|U_{\mu1}|^2 |U_{\tau2}|^2 - |U_{\mu2}|^2 |U_{\tau1}|^2 \right) \right]^2$$

◆ The three solutions can be explicitly expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \eta_e \\ \eta_\mu \\ \eta_\tau \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{D_0} \begin{pmatrix} C_{ee} & C_{e\mu} & C_{e\tau} \\ C_{\mu e} & C_{\mu\mu} & C_{\mu\tau} \\ C_{\tau e} & C_{\tau\mu} & C_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_e \\ f_\mu \\ f_\tau \end{bmatrix}$$

The nine coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ee} &= (|U_{\mu 1}|^2 |U_{\tau 2}|^2 - |U_{\mu 2}|^2 |U_{\tau 1}|^2)^2 \\ &+ (|U_{\mu 2}|^2 |U_{\tau 3}|^2 - |U_{\mu 3}|^2 |U_{\tau 2}|^2)^2 \\ &+ (|U_{\mu 3}|^2 |U_{\tau 1}|^2 - |U_{\mu 1}|^2 |U_{\tau 3}|^2)^2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mu\mu} &= (|U_{\tau 1}|^2 |U_{e 2}|^2 - |U_{\tau 2}|^2 |U_{e 1}|^2)^2 \\ &+ (|U_{\tau 2}|^2 |U_{e 3}|^2 - |U_{\tau 3}|^2 |U_{e 2}|^2)^2 \\ &+ (|U_{\tau 3}|^2 |U_{e 1}|^2 - |U_{\tau 1}|^2 |U_{e 3}|^2)^2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\tau\tau} &= (|U_{e 1}|^2 |U_{\mu 2}|^2 - |U_{e 2}|^2 |U_{\mu 1}|^2)^2 \\ &+ (|U_{e 2}|^2 |U_{\mu 3}|^2 - |U_{e 3}|^2 |U_{\mu 2}|^2)^2 \\ &+ (|U_{e 3}|^2 |U_{\mu 1}|^2 - |U_{e 1}|^2 |U_{\mu 3}|^2)^2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{e\mu} = C_{\mu e} &= (|U_{\mu 1}|^2 |U_{\tau 2}|^2 - |U_{\mu 2}|^2 |U_{\tau 1}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{\tau 1}|^2 |U_{e 2}|^2 - |U_{\tau 2}|^2 |U_{e 1}|^2) \\ &+ (|U_{\mu 2}|^2 |U_{\tau 3}|^2 - |U_{\mu 3}|^2 |U_{\tau 2}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{\tau 2}|^2 |U_{e 3}|^2 - |U_{\tau 3}|^2 |U_{e 2}|^2) \\ &+ (|U_{\mu 3}|^2 |U_{\tau 1}|^2 - |U_{\mu 1}|^2 |U_{\tau 3}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{\tau 3}|^2 |U_{e 1}|^2 - |U_{\tau 1}|^2 |U_{e 3}|^2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{e\tau} = C_{\tau e} &= (|U_{e 1}|^2 |U_{\mu 2}|^2 - |U_{e 2}|^2 |U_{\mu 1}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{\mu 1}|^2 |U_{\tau 2}|^2 - |U_{\mu 2}|^2 |U_{\tau 1}|^2) \\ &+ (|U_{e 2}|^2 |U_{\mu 3}|^2 - |U_{e 3}|^2 |U_{\mu 2}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{\mu 2}|^2 |U_{\tau 3}|^2 - |U_{\mu 3}|^2 |U_{\tau 2}|^2) \\ &+ (|U_{e 3}|^2 |U_{\mu 1}|^2 - |U_{e 1}|^2 |U_{\mu 3}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{\mu 3}|^2 |U_{\tau 1}|^2 - |U_{\mu 1}|^2 |U_{\tau 3}|^2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mu\tau} = C_{\tau\mu} &= (|U_{\tau 1}|^2 |U_{e 2}|^2 - |U_{\tau 2}|^2 |U_{e 1}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{e 1}|^2 |U_{\mu 2}|^2 - |U_{e 2}|^2 |U_{\mu 1}|^2) \\ &+ (|U_{\tau 2}|^2 |U_{e 3}|^2 - |U_{\tau 3}|^2 |U_{e 2}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{e 2}|^2 |U_{\mu 3}|^2 - |U_{e 3}|^2 |U_{\mu 2}|^2) \\ &+ (|U_{\tau 3}|^2 |U_{e 1}|^2 - |U_{\tau 1}|^2 |U_{e 3}|^2) \\ &\times (|U_{e 3}|^2 |U_{\mu 1}|^2 - |U_{e 1}|^2 |U_{\mu 3}|^2). \end{aligned}$$

◆ From the **source** to the **telescope**:

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_e \\ f_\mu \\ f_\tau \end{bmatrix} \simeq \begin{pmatrix} 0.5526 & 0.2125 & 0.2348 \\ 0.2125 & 0.4078 & 0.3797 \\ 0.2348 & 0.3797 & 0.3855 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \eta_e \\ \eta_\mu \\ \eta_\tau \end{bmatrix}$$

Nothing looks strange.

◆ From the **telescope** to the **source**:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \eta_e \\ \eta_\mu \\ \eta_\tau \end{bmatrix} \simeq \begin{pmatrix} 2.505 & 1.392 & -2.897 \\ 1.392 & 30.41 & -30.80 \\ -2.897 & -30.80 & 34.70 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_e \\ f_\mu \\ f_\tau \end{bmatrix}$$

Cancellation between two big numbers.

◆ Origin of **divergence**: approximate **mu-tau**:

An exact **mu-tau** symmetry:

$$|U_{\mu 1}| = |U_{\tau 1}|, \quad |U_{\mu 2}| = |U_{\tau 2}|, \quad |U_{\mu 3}| = |U_{\tau 3}|$$

$$\begin{aligned} |U_{e1}|^2 &= c_{12}^2 c_{13}^2, & |U_{e2}|^2 &= s_{12}^2 c_{13}^2, & |U_{e3}|^2 &= s_{13}^2, \\ |U_{\mu 1}|^2 &= s_{12}^2 c_{23}^2 + c_{12}^2 s_{13}^2 s_{23}^2 + 2c_{12}s_{12}s_{13}c_{23}s_{23} \cos \delta_\nu, \\ |U_{\mu 2}|^2 &= c_{12}^2 c_{23}^2 + s_{12}^2 s_{13}^2 s_{23}^2 - 2c_{12}s_{12}s_{13}c_{23}s_{23} \cos \delta_\nu, \\ |U_{\tau 1}|^2 &= s_{12}^2 s_{23}^2 + c_{12}^2 s_{13}^2 c_{23}^2 - 2c_{12}s_{12}s_{13}c_{23}s_{23} \cos \delta_\nu, \\ |U_{\tau 2}|^2 &= c_{12}^2 s_{23}^2 + s_{12}^2 s_{13}^2 c_{23}^2 + 2c_{12}s_{12}s_{13}c_{23}s_{23} \cos \delta_\nu, \\ |U_{\mu 3}|^2 &= c_{13}^2 s_{23}^2, & |U_{\tau 3}|^2 &= c_{13}^2 c_{23}^2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} s_{12}^2 &= 3.03 \times 10^{-1}, & s_{13}^2 &= 2.23 \times 10^{-2}, & s_{23}^2 &= 4.73 \times 10^{-1} \\ \delta_\nu &= 1.20 \times \pi \quad (\mathbf{F. Capozzi et al, 2503.07752}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_0 &= \left[|U_{e1}|^2 (|U_{\mu 2}|^2 |U_{\tau 3}|^2 - |U_{\mu 3}|^2 |U_{\tau 2}|^2) \right. \\ &+ |U_{e2}|^2 (|U_{\mu 3}|^2 |U_{\tau 1}|^2 - |U_{\mu 1}|^2 |U_{\tau 3}|^2) \\ &\left. + |U_{e3}|^2 (|U_{\mu 1}|^2 |U_{\tau 2}|^2 - |U_{\mu 2}|^2 |U_{\tau 1}|^2) \right]^2 \end{aligned}$$

- ◆ From the **source** to the **telescope**:

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_e \\ f_\mu \\ f_\tau \end{bmatrix} \simeq \begin{pmatrix} 0.5526 & 0.2125 & 0.2348 \\ 0.2125 & 0.4078 & 0.3797 \\ 0.2348 & 0.3797 & 0.3855 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \eta_e \\ \eta_\mu \\ \eta_\tau \end{bmatrix} \longrightarrow$$

- ◆ Assuming the standard **source** flavors:

$$\eta_e = 1/3, \eta_\mu = 2/3 \text{ and } \eta_\tau = 0$$

getting **democratic telescope** flavors:

$$f_e \simeq 0.326, f_\mu \simeq 0.343 \text{ and } f_\tau \simeq 0.331$$

- ◆ From the **telescope** to the **source**:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \eta_e \\ \eta_\mu \\ \eta_\tau \end{bmatrix} \simeq \begin{pmatrix} 2.505 & 1.392 & -2.897 \\ 1.392 & 30.41 & -30.80 \\ -2.897 & -30.80 & 34.70 \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_e \\ f_\mu \\ f_\tau \end{bmatrix} \longrightarrow$$

- ◆ Inputting the **IceCube** result with the same **source** flavor ratio assumption:

$$f_e : f_\mu : f_\tau = 0.30 : 0.37 : 0.33$$

obtaining **nonsense telescope** flavors:

$$\eta_e \simeq 0.31, \eta_\mu \simeq 1.50 \text{ and } \eta_\tau \simeq -0.81$$

their sum is OK

- ◆ What is probably **wrong**?

- The assumption of the same source flavor composition is invalid.
- Current IceCube data are not accurate enough. **Most likely!**
- Both of them, together with some other possible reasons.

◆ The exact **mu-tau** symmetry implies:

$$\theta_{23} = \pi/4 \text{ and } \delta_\nu = -\pi/2$$

$$P_{e\mu} = P_{e\tau}, \quad P_{\mu\mu} = P_{\mu\tau} = P_{\tau\tau}$$

$$f_\tau = f_\mu \longrightarrow$$

$$\begin{cases} P_{ee}\eta_e + P_{e\mu}(\eta_\mu + \eta_\tau) = f_e \\ P_{e\mu}\eta_e + P_{\mu\mu}(\eta_\mu + \eta_\tau) = f_\mu \end{cases}$$

In this case only two **original** flavor ratios can be inferred (**ZZX, 2511.15127**):

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\eta_e} &= \frac{P_{\mu\mu}}{P_{ee}P_{\mu\mu} - P_{e\mu}^2} f_e - \frac{P_{e\mu}}{P_{ee}P_{\mu\mu} - P_{e\mu}^2} f_\mu \\ &= \frac{1 - c_{12}^2 s_{12}^2 c_{13}^4 - c_{13}^2 s_{13}^2}{1 - 3c_{12}^2 s_{12}^2 c_{13}^4 - 3c_{13}^2 s_{13}^2} f_e \\ &\quad - \frac{2(c_{12}^2 s_{12}^2 c_{13}^4 + c_{13}^2 s_{13}^2)}{1 - 3c_{12}^2 s_{12}^2 c_{13}^4 - 3c_{13}^2 s_{13}^2} f_\mu, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\eta_\mu + \eta_\tau} &= \frac{P_{ee}}{P_{ee}P_{\mu\mu} - P_{e\mu}^2} f_\mu - \frac{P_{e\mu}}{P_{ee}P_{\mu\mu} - P_{e\mu}^2} f_e \\ &= 2 \left[\frac{1 - 2c_{12}^2 s_{12}^2 c_{13}^4 - 2c_{13}^2 s_{13}^2}{1 - 3c_{12}^2 s_{12}^2 c_{13}^4 - 3c_{13}^2 s_{13}^2} f_\mu \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{c_{12}^2 s_{12}^2 c_{13}^4 + c_{13}^2 s_{13}^2}{1 - 3c_{12}^2 s_{12}^2 c_{13}^4 - 3c_{13}^2 s_{13}^2} f_e \right], \end{aligned}$$

◆ Numerical illustration:

JUNO (2511.14593) : $s_{12}^2 = 3.092 \times 10^{-1}$

Daya Bay (2211.14988) : $s_{13}^2 = 2.175 \times 10^{-2}$

$$\longrightarrow \begin{cases} \eta_e \simeq 2.398 f_e - 1.398 f_\mu, \\ \eta_\mu + \eta_\tau \simeq 3.398 f_\mu - 1.398 f_e \end{cases}$$

- ◆ **Nine moduli of the PMNS matrix elements constrained from data at the 3σ level:**

the area of each circle = an element's modulus

P. Harrison, W. Scott (2002):
mu-tau reflection symmetry
 with both $\theta_{23} = \pi/4$ & $\delta = -\pi/2$

- ◆ **The standard parametrization of the PMNS matrix with 3 Euler-like mixing angles and 3 CPV phases:**

PMNS =

$$U_0 = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & \hat{s}_{12}^*c_{13} & \hat{s}_{13}^* \\ -\hat{s}_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}\hat{s}_{13}\hat{s}_{23}^* & c_{12}c_{23} - \hat{s}_{12}^*\hat{s}_{13}\hat{s}_{23}^* & c_{13}\hat{s}_{23}^* \\ \hat{s}_{12}\hat{s}_{23} - c_{12}\hat{s}_{13}c_{23} & -c_{12}\hat{s}_{23} - \hat{s}_{12}^*\hat{s}_{13}c_{23} & c_{13}c_{23} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\theta_{23} \sim \pi/4 \oplus \begin{cases} \theta_{13} \ll 1 \\ \text{OR} \\ \delta \equiv \delta_{13} - \delta_{12} - \delta_{23} \sim \pm\pi/2 \end{cases}$$

We are on the right track

$$|U_{\mu i}| \simeq |U_{\tau i}| \quad (i = 1, 2, 3)$$

◆ To get a **balance** between **model building (easy)** and **data fitting (good)**, I bet on the **TM1** pattern of lepton flavor mixing (**ZZX, S. Zhou, hep-ph/0607302; C.S. Lam, hep-ph/0611017; many models**).

◆ **TM1 predictions:** $\sin^2 \theta_{12} = \frac{1}{3} (1 - 2 \tan^2 \theta_{13})$, $\theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}$, $\delta = -\frac{\pi}{2}$. **Slight symmetry breaking.**

◆ Today we bet on a data-driven μ - τ **reflection symmetry**, and have tried many simple or complicated flavor groups for model building. It is true that the tastes of quite a lot of theorists seem exotic and strange, but such a **minimal flavor symmetry** has a good chance to be the truth.

◆ High energy astrophysical neutrinos are useful tools to probe the **hadronic origin** of cosmic rays. But to infer the **flavor composition** of a given source from the telescope data, sufficient precisions and accuracies are needed due to the approximate **PMNS μ - τ reflection symmetry**.

MANY THANKS